

Review Article

The Concept of Love in the Old Testament Salvation History: A Panacea for the 21st Century Development

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Abstract

Love is a fundamental concept in the Old Testament. It extends from sexual love to the love between God and man expressed within the concept of Covenant relationship. This paper therefore, examined the term love in the Old Testament salvation history, such as the meaning, etymological usage, secular and religious love. The review paper critically examined these points with the view to discussing what love in the Old Testament actually entails and how it can be emulated.

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Introduction

The Bible says God is love. The book of John says, “We know how much God loves us and we have put our trust in him. God is love, and all we live in love, live in God and God in them”, (1st John 4:16). Therefore, love is a character of God. Love is the fundamental concept in the Old Testament. It extends from sexual love to the love between God and humanity expressed within the concept of covenant relationship. God told the community of Israel that:

But then I will win her back once again. I will lead her out into the desert and speak tenderly to her there. I will return her vine yards to her and transform the valley of trouble into a gateway of hope. She will give herself to me there, as she did long ago when she was young, when I freed her from captivity in Egypt. (Hos.2:14-15).

This paper examines the term love in the Old Testament salvation history. It will evaluate the meaning, etymological usage, secular and religious love.

Meaning

Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (1978), defines love “as a strong feeling of fondness for another person especially between members of a family or between people of opposite sexes”. To Cassell’s English Dictionary (1968), Love is “a feeling of deep regard, fondness and devotion, deep affection usually accompanied by yearning or desire for, affection between persons of opposite sexes, more or less founded on or combined with desire or position”. However, Claud (1978) says that:

The word love actually signifies a mixture of different things: carnal or spiritual, passionate or thoughtful, serious or light, expensive or destructive. It is not simply an emotion but the total quality of relationship. In its personal character, love is closely related to the sexual realm even when the subject is God’s Love.

Therefore, love is a force which initiates and maintains relationship, be it among persons or between God and man. However, the Old Testament idea of the concept of love is determined by the New Testament idea of love and grace, because it includes the relationships of friendship, sex, covenant, loyalty, kindness and sometimes mercy and pity.

The Etymology of Love in the Old Testament

According to Good, (1962), a number of words are used in the Old Testament to express the various aspects of love. The most important of these is by the root “ahabh” and its derivation “ahabh”, “ahabhah”, “ahabhim”. It is a word which denotes both human and divine love, sometimes with sexual connotation. Thus, the word “ahabh” and its cognates are used in a variety of context, which are much the same as the uses of the English word Love. According to Meckenzie (1978):

Love basically signifies a voluntary attachment which is used somewhat improperly as the English word is used of attachment to objects or to love between the sexes.

The etymology of “ahabh” is not certain, Good (1962) says:

There exists insufficient information as to the original meaning of this root. Its primary connection with sexual love is suggested, but not proved by animal derivation. For

example; "ahabh" is used for carnal love as in Hosea 8:9 and "ahabh" is equally used in Hosea 9:10 for idolatrous love.

"Ahabh" can signify the natural love of the father for his child, (Gen.22:2), of spouse for each other (24:6-7), it can also mean friendship or the dependence of slaves upon the benevolence of their masters, (Ex.21:5), or even sexual passion (II Sam.13:1, 4, 15). But it can also mean love of one's neighbours (Lev.19:18) or of strangers (19:34) and above all of God . . . "Ahabh" can even be used for the love which God offers to man especially to the people of Israel (Deut.4:37).

Love is thus, shown in the Old Testament to be fundamentally a spontaneous feeling which impels one to self-sacrifice or in the case of things to grasping the object which awakens desire or to performing the action which gives pleasure. Thus an affectional feeling in the physical realm was applied to emotional stimulation which produced it. Wallis, (1974), buttresses this point by saying "the emotional experience is the germ cell for the development of the concept of "ahabh".

The scope of the concept of love in the Old Testament idiom is very broad; it extends from the affection of members of the opposite sexes for one another to the relationship between Yahweh and Israel. In fact, this may be the climax of the root "ahabh" in the Old Testament salvation history. It indicates total love which demands all of one's energy based on Yahweh's love for Israel which motivates him to save and to punish them.

Walli (1974) says, "Ahabh" and its cognates in the Old Testament have a striking pragmatic character. It presupposes a concrete inner disposition which is based on experience and events. Love also includes a conscious act on behalf of the person who is loved, or the thing preferred. Meckenzie, (1978) upholds that "love in this sense has a sociological basis". An Old Testament text can be speaking of love even when the word 'ahabh' is not actually used, but the attitude of love is clearly described in the context. For example, people are enjoined to love their enemies in passages like "If your enemy is hungry, give him bread to eat and if thirsty give him water to drink" (Pro.25:21). Or "if you meet your enemy's ox or his ass going astray, you shall bring it back to him . . . (Ex.23:41). It is precisely in such acts of love that the command to love can be seen in proper perspective, when love is both demanded which a humanitarian spirit makes on a person and rooted in the divine command to love.

Theologically, love appears as a mutual sentiment between Yahweh and Israel. This is clearly seen in Hosea who gave it form in the analogy of the marriage of Yahweh and Israel. A significant feature of this analogy is that the initiative in matrimonial love often comes from the man and not from the woman, subsequently, Yahweh is the first to love Israel and Israel's love is a response.

The love of Yahweh for Israel re-occurs in several passages in Deuteronomy and books influenced by the Deuteronomy redaction. The idea of love and election appears also in Isaiah (43:4), Malachi (1:24), and in the Psalm's (47:5). Apart from Yahweh love for Israel, the command for Israel to love Yahweh is also very prominent especially in Exodus (20:6) and Deuteronomy (5:10). This summary on the theological concept of love is necessary to lead us to the concept of Old Testament love.

Love in the Old Testament Salvation History

Love is a pervasive attribute of human relations in the Old Testament. It takes various form: the sexual or romantic, the love within families and within bonds of kinship, the love of friendship and human, the covenant with the personal and active character of human love is the view of divine love in the Old Testament. God's love is his redeeming activity in human history, tagged salvation history. This actively produces the relationship of persons, between man and God. Thus, love has both secular and religious connotation.

Secular Love

We shall examine secular love as follows:- sex, family and friend and neighbour and enemies

Sex: on its most elementary level love is a sexual relationship. Wallis (1974) maintains that in the Old Testament, "ahabh" is also used when referring to sexual love, or to marital relationship as sometime given at creation in a positive sense, although a different root "yadha" is used for the act of sexual intercourse itself. He further stated that the primary of the sexual relationship in the nature of man is evident in both "P" and "J" creation stories. Thus, Genesis (1:28) seems to imply what man is in the image of God in his nature as male and female. This is further suggested by the importance of the term knowledge as a symbol of both men's relationship of man and woman as we find in the statement "now Adam knows his wife" (Gen.4:1).

Other examples of romantic love in the Old Testament are Isaac is fond of Rebecca (Gen.24:67), Jacob of Rachael (29:18, 20, 30), etc. and according to Ecclesiastes (9:9), "know

nothing better to recommend than the time which man enjoys with his wife whom he love". Finally, Proverbs says:

Let your wife be a fountain of blessing for you. Rejoice in the wife of your youth. She is a loving doe, a grateful deer. Let her breast satisfy you always. May you always be captivated by her love, (Pro.5:18-19).

The love between man and woman and especially that which binds husband and wife together, is simply recognized as the given of nature, with no suggestion of a lack of restraint. It is disastrous when one does not control his or her emotion but in unbridled passion acts in a way contrary to genuine love, thereby hurting the person he loves and violating the law of chastity. For example, the stories of Amnon in I Samuel 13:1-9, where he filled with sexual desire over Tamar and David's sexual desire over Bathsheba (II Sam.11).

Therefore, love that is not consciously aware of the importance of behaviour, but strives to enjoy life without self-restraints must inevitably lead to complications and should be rejected. Thus, it can be said that our individual conception and understanding of the word love primarily has sexual tines.

Love among Family and Friends

The Old Testament like our own languages uses the root "ahabh" to connect things, which naturally have nothing to do with each other's. In this sense, one can conveniently say that they are employed as metaphor that is connoting personal attachment other than sex. For instance, David says, "I am distress for you, my brother Jonathan, very pleasant have you been to me, your love to me was wonderful, passing the love of woman", (ii Sam.1:26).

Therefore, Wallis, (1974), says:

The strong emotional characteristics of the concept of love are quite illuminating in description of the relationship between the generations, between masters and servants and of the relationship between men.

These feelings, he asserts may indeed belong completely to the realm of the original emotion of love and friendship, adding that there is also the dangers of sudden change into the opposite hate. For instance Isaac loved Esau probably because of the savoury game which Esau killed, whereas Rebecca loved Jacob (Gen.25:27), and this led to hatred

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between Jacob and Esau. Also, Jacob's overbearing love for Joseph made other sons of Jacob to hate Joseph (Gen.31:3ff). Sometimes exclusiveness of love may be the point where hatred can enter. Love must be responsible as well as devoted.

In the Old Testament, there were also tribal and familial bonds. These were significant elements in the relationship of kinship. It is related to sexual love in Ruth 3:10 where "hesedh" (loyalty, kindness) involved both the initiative of sexual love and the loyalty to the next-of-kin. The social life of man in the Old Testament is very important area of human relationship. Just as the basic social units of family and tribe are maintained by love the quality of life most desirable in man is that of "hesedh". Though the word has primary religious connotations, they are extended to man's responsibility in the whole of society. Good, (1962), asserts, "When rich show no kindness to the poor, when the friend shuns and despises his friend, when love is lavished on those who hate others, the society is in danger."

Love for Neighbours/Enemies

Sometimes people think of love in only one direction that is they love those who loved them and forget about other aspects of love. Love should be extended to all sphere of life. Quell and Stauffer (1969) maintain:

That love is regarded as "inseparable from humanity and therefore, set forth as the norm of social relationship which is included within the scope and shelter of the divine law". Thus "you shall love your neighbour as yourself" (Lev.19:18) is in form of law and contains the clearly defined term neighbour, note it is not strictly a law, because love is a matter of feeling and cannot be legally commanded.

The Old Testament considers the care of one's own life and possessions to include maintaining the existence of one's own family and tribe. It used this effort to preserve oneself as a standard for measuring one's love for one's fellow man.

Wallis (1974), notes that if the feeling of love expresses a genuine deep-rooted bond with mankind in general, then naturally it must have a concrete connection with a person's interest. Consequently, the Old Testament advocates the kind of behaviour which equates concern for the wellbeing of one's neighbour with the assertion of one's own will.

From the human point of view, the same neighbour can even mean an enemy. This seems most likely in the light of a comparison of Deuteronomy 22:1-4, with Ex.23:4f.

Deuteronomy prescribes help to an enemy. Whatever may be the relationship between the two passages, the comparison justifies us in including the love of enemies in Leviticus 19:18. Whether the neighbour may be a friend or an enemy, the right attitude to him should be of love and no legality.

'Ahabh' designates a positive relationship to a specific kind of behaviour be it good or bad. Therefore, from the highest level of sexual communion to the ordinary attachment of kindness, the appropriate order of human relationship is one of mutuality in love.

Divine or Religious Love

Love in the Old Testament has a rich-theological significance. As a theological concept, Viktor (1976), says "they are God's love to man, man's love to God and love between man seen as a religious duty". Therefore, biblical thought is theocentric ally oriented, and has as its central point the idea of God as creator and Lord to all mankind.

God's Love to Man

Love appears as a sentiment between Yahweh and Israel, and God's actions in history are spoken of in terms of his saving activities in the life of Israel. Therefore, two concepts surface that is, Election and Covenant. Election and Covenant are acts of God's love in salvation history of the Old Testament, without clear-cut distinction between them. The Old Testament writers have firm conviction that God chose Israel rather than Israel chose God. However, the distinction between election and covenant is a narrow one. The two are closely related.

According to Merriam Webster's Collegiate Dictionary (2002), "election is an act or process of electing some thing or somebody." Therefore, love as an election of God, can be said to be a divine action.

Love as Election: Packer, (1982), says that:

The main Old Testament word designates that of election is the verb "bahar" which expresses the idea of choice of someone or something out of a multiple of possibilities. Israelite's faith was founded on the belief that Israel was God's chosen people, the source of which was God's free omnipotent love.

Edmond, (1967), acknowledges that:

Election is one of the central realities of the Old Testament. It is the initial act by which Yahweh comes into relation with Israel and the permanent reality, which assures the constancy of the bond. Every intervention by God in history is an election. Either when he chooses a place in where to make more special manifestation of his presence, or when he chooses a people to carry out his intentions, or when he chooses a man to be his representative as a messenger, the Old Testament God is the one who has universal sovereignty as his disposal and shows it by the free use that he makes of it.

The patriarchal and Sinai covenant are the basis for the election. Israel's existence lies solely on the election grace of God. If Yahweh had not delivered her out of the bondage of Pharaoh, Israel's history as we have it today would probably have come to nothing. This fact makes her conscious of her relationship with Yahweh thereby, forming the basis of her theological thinking.

The theology of election implies an exclusive bond between Yahweh and Israel. God created all nations of the world, but he chooses Israel as his heritage. What prompted God to choose Israel? Was it because of her righteousness or that she was better than the other nations? Deuteronomy 7:6-8, says:

For you are a holy people ,holy to the Lord your God, the Lord your God has chosen you to be a people for his own possession out of all the peoples that are on the face of the earth. It was not because you were more in number than any other people that the Lord set his love upon you and chose you and is keeping the oath which he swore to your fathers . . .”.

Thus, the choice is entirely the initiative of God. Therefore, God's redemption of Israel is the love which upholds the precious thing he has created.

Covenant Love

Covenant is an agreement between two parties. It can be between superiors and inferior, or between two equal partners.

Brandon (1970), maintains that:

The idea of covenant between God and Israel is basic to salvation history. In fact, the idea of covenant relationship characterized Israelite religion and was constantly evoked by the prophets.

Thus, Eichrodt (1975) takes covenant "as the central idea of the Old Testament, salvation history".

The most frequent word for covenant is 'berith'. However, there are numerous references to covenant and covenant relationships where this term does not occur. This word is very complex and many scholars have expressed doubt as to whether one can succeed in providing an adequate and convincing etymology of the term "berith." The door remains open to several possibilities". Therefore, our concern in this paper is love, so we do not intend to give a full etymology of the word (covenant) rather we are concern about the understanding of the concept as it relates to God's Love in the Old Testament.

According to Mac Cullock, (1959):

Covenant is "a bind or agreement entered into between two persons or group of persons or between a man or a group of men and a god or gods". The covenant thus entered upon may be for a specific time or for all times, it may cover certain clearly defined purposes or it may be infinite. Covenant may be between parties of different socio-political groups in which case the covenant creates a relationship between them regulated by the terms of the covenant.

Therefore, we can say that covenant is an agreement or bond entered into by two or more persons. It could be parity or suzerainty covenants. Suzerainty covenant is a covenant between a deity and man for example, we see God making covenant with Abraham (Gen.12:1-3, 15:10-21), or a group of people as in the case of Sinai covenant, (Exo.19:5-6). When the covenant is between Yahweh and man, it is evident that the parties are not equal terms at all.

Herbert, (1968) says:

On God's part the covenant is a declaration of his ordinances for man and an admission of man into a special relation with him. While to man, there can be only be the duty of obedience and grateful response.

The covenant relationship with God and Israel at Sinai is identical with that which was later pictured by Prophet Hosea as a relation of wife and husband. "Ahabh" and the figure of marriage point behind and beneath the covenant to its motives and origin in the innermost personal being of God. His love is part of the mystery of his personality. In Hosea 11:9, the Old Testament come very near to saying that "God is love". Whatever role the idea of a covenant between God and Israel may have played in ancient Israelite thought there is much to be said as Robert (1980) puts it "covenant theology was developed in the seventh century by the Deuteronomist." Deuteronomy in particular bases the covenant relationship between Israel and God's Prior Love. It incorporates the idea of love in a systematic way into its thought and it remains the Old Testament book in which the conception has its largest place.

We can see that the cause of God's love for Israel lies in the personal being of God himself. In fact, God's love seeks moral fellowship with Israel. It cannot be separated from his righteousness and it is not sentimental. Quell G and Stanffer (1969) say "over against Israel's sin, God's love is expressed in judgment and forgiveness". God's punishment of sin is not a contradiction with his love. The severity was never separated from tenderness (Hosea 11:8). Though strict justice demanded Israel's destruction, God refused to do so, because of the mystery of his divine love. This love with which he loved his people is ever lasting and universal.

Therefore, one can sum up the entire history of the encounter of Israel with God as one of covenant love. This attribute is the dominating motive in the acts of God. Love is the attribute that gives God personal identity and it is the key to understanding his character.

Man's Love to God: In Old Testament, the love God bestowed on man is for the most part understood as faithfulness to the covenant terms. Therefore, it is not surprising that the reciprocal love of man should also be conceived of as consisting essentially on the acceptance of covenant obligations. According to Gran field (1966), "man's love to God is not something independence But rather it is something dependence on God's prior love". The response of man to God's love is his gratitude for what God has done for him.

Man's love to God is the typical mark of the devout man of the Old Testament and it is commended in the Shema (Deut.6:5). This love is expressed in ethical terms, in obedience to God. Love towards God is associated with keeping his commandment (Ex.20:6), serving him, walking in his ways and fearing him - (Deut.10:12). Therefore, to fear is to have reverence and honour for God. To walk is to emulate God in all matters of conduct

and human relationships. To love is to have hidden affection and emotions dedicated to God. And to serve is to engage in acts of worship, which is outlined in the scripture.

Basically, to love God is to have pleasure in him and to seek him instinctively. Those who love God are basically the pious whose life of faith bears stamps of originality. Abraham is called a friend of God because his intimate intercourse with God and that mark him out as a model of piety. Love for God is simply to be understood as love for one's neighbour and as such it is something to be pursued or cultivated for its own sake. Love for God therefore, seeks the whole personality of man and it is God's demand.

Love between Men as a Religious Duty

The love of men for each other is likewise motivated by covenant ideas. Mutual steadfast love and faithfulness is essential in human relationships. Love between man and man is seen as a duty before God. This injunction is rooted in the prior love of God to man. Part of man's response for his men gratitude is by loving his fellow man. It is commanded by God. The Old Testament commandment of love the neighbour (Lev. 19:18), is clearly unsentimental and practical. Love is ordained by God, to be the normal ideal human relationship, and as such, it is given the sanction of the divine law.

Thus love is identical with peace. When the counsel of peace prevails between two persons then there is love, because the will is identical with each other.

We can conveniently say that the love of God is primary and man loves God and man in response to God's love. But the life of love is a life lived out in accordance to the relationship of the covenant. This is necessary in order that man may have a frame work in which he orders his devoted obedience.

Conclusion

This paper examined the concept of love in the Old Testament salvation history. It is evident that the place of love in the Old Testament forms the basis of every relation. Whether human or divine, love is the deepest possible expression of the closeness of personal relation.

In the secular sense "ahabh" is most commonly employed of the mutual urges of the sexes in which case there is no restraint or sense of uncleanness. It is also used of a multitude of personal and sub-personal relations which have no connection with the sexual impulses. Fundamentally, it is an inner force which impels to performing the action

which gives pleasure or obtaining the action which gives awakens desire. The fact has been established that the divine love which is the basis for the Old Testament saving history is not a man sentiment, but a creative energy. The concept of love is unique. Therefore, we should look beyond carnal sex and sexuality when the word love is mentioned.

Thus, God is love, as the love of a father for whom every human being is an offspring, every living being a creature and everything a personal creation, is alone worthy of complete emulation.

Recommendation

Man was created in the image of God. Since, man is created in the image of God; he should emulate this good character of God. Therefore, as children of God, humanity should exhibit love to all. The Bible says "this is the message we have heard from the beginning: We should love one another." (1 John 3:11). Love covers every evil thing in the universe, so let us all love one another.

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